

Al-Labli's Responses In His Book (In Order To Hope To Know The Receptors Of The Verbs)

Ghaidaa Kadhim Abdullah

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 06, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: November 08, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Al-Labli's, Grammar, Intellectual Critical</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5669213</p>	<p><i>Arise beside intellectual giving codified grammar an intellectual critical color that represent by scrutiny rules and responses to them ,so what are the intellectual debates among linguists only a form of responses, The third and fourth centuries AH witnessed an intellectual flourishing , scientists did not shy away from that time period from forwarding responses and objection to those who preceded them from the grammarians or even for those who are contemporary with them As we find responses for furs)t207h), On Alkasae (t189h), and responses for Mubarrad (t285h), on Sibawayh(t180h), on morphological and grammatical issues and responses by Ibn Jinni (t392h), on Al-mazni)t247h), in adverbial positions , later eras also witnessed the emergence of dependable works in authoring it on the employment responses, including the book equity in matters of dispute to Abi Al-Barakat Al-Anbari (t577h), And the Al-Nusra coalition in the different areas of Kufa Basra for Zubeidi (t803h), in this research, a group of Allaby's responses (t691h), he responded by the opinions of scholars and their criticism, I collected it from the book (bghiat alamal fi maerifat mustaqbalat alafeal). These responses depend on the foundations specific to Allbali, It is the basis of the mental represented by his dependence on the bug in the response, Morphological grammar, Homogenization in Al-Aalal, And a linguistic base represented by the words of the imams of the language, Contained from the words of the Arabs, And a semantic anchor represented by the context. Allebli responded in his responses to leading scholars such as Sebawayh. And he often declared who responded to them, Except in two places used (they said: and many grammarians), The word for his responses is usually the word (wrong) the word (weak), (if he had alleged), and (not as he said)</i></p>

Introduction

Preface / It is necessary to present an overview of the life and biography of Al-Labli

His name and lineage:

Al-Lubli is Ahmed bin Yusuf bin Yaqoub bin Ali Al-Fihri Al-Lubli, and he was nicknamed Abu Jaafar, one of the scholars of the seventh century. Ten (1), he was born in Bulbul (2) in the year 613 A.H. (3), to whom he belongs. It is located in the south of Andalusia, in the west of Seville. It was known for its prestigious renaissance, as it was the capital of a small state founded by Ahmed bin Yahya al-Yahsabi (d. 434 AH) (4).

His life:

Libli left his city Liblah; Because of the successive wars and conflicts on this city, and Bejaia lived and read for a period of time (5), And then to Tunisia. And he had a trip to the east, and he passed through Egypt, the Levant, and the Hijaz, then he returned and settled in Tunisia until he died.

Old age:

He was educated by the most knowledgeable Abu Ishaq Ibrahim AlBatusi (died 637 AH), Ali bin Jaber Al-Dabbaj (died 646 AH), and Abu Ali Omar bin Abdullah Al-Shalubini (died 645 AH). The most important of his non-Andalusian sheikhs is Abdul Aziz bin Abdul Salam. Ibn Abd al-Qasim al-Dimashqi Izz al-Din al-Sulami (died 660 AH) (6).

his disciples:

His most famous disciples were Abu Hayyan Muhammad bin Yusuf bin Ali (d. 654 AH), Ibn Rashid, the owner of the journey, and Ibn Jaber. The owner of the index.) (7).

His writings :

Al-Labli's books include: Al-Ilaam Bidood al-Salam in Logic, Lifting Talbes on the Knowledge of Naturalization, and Aiming. Hopes to know the pronunciation of all the receptors of verbs in the language. The masterpiece of explicit glory in explaining the book Al-Faseeh, and. Explanation of the writer's literature, and the belief of the believer in theology. and action receptors. And the halal was mentioned in explaining the verses of the sentences in grammar and other things (8).

His death:

Al-Ajl passed away in Tunisia in the year (691 AH) after returning to it from his journey (9).

The responses of the libli were characterized by a variety of characteristics, namely:

1-Relying on the bug in response:

Al-Lubli employed the defect in his responses to be conclusive evidence for the correctness of his response, including his reliance on the bug (security of confusion) in his response. His response to Abu Ubaid in the future of the verb (to beard) said:)) Abu Ubaid made a mistake in his book Al-Gharib al-Ghareeb on this subject. Kind, he said: His beard. So he made the future of my beard a beard, and this is a mistake because my beard is from the daughters of Yaa and the daughters of the Yaa Its future is on the verb with the fracture and not on the verb with the accusative so as not to be confused with the daughters of the waw. So he does this by adding the blocks of waw, and he does that .By breaking the blocks of Z has progressed. Rather, analogy is his beard and his beard, and his beard is the future of his beard, and his beard is the future of the beard, and his beard is the future. A whale The distinction between the daughters of Ya'a (his beard is aliyah) and the daughters of the waw (his beard is alahah), because the verb (lihy) in its linguistic origin has Two meanings: the first is a member of the organs, and the second is the peeling of the thing (11) and the second meaning (the peeling of the thing) has developed. semantic to become in the sense of blame (12) also, and the analogy is in the past of the verb (beard) in the sense of blame only with ya, as for the past The verb (beard) in the sense of peeling, it is Balya and waw (13) and in this Ibn Manzur (14) and Al-Zubaidi transmitted on the authority of Al-Kisa'i:) He said Al-Kisa'i said: The man's beard is bearded with blame and nothing else, and the lute's beard has waved with Yaa and the waw (15) and this is evidence However, al-Labli was right in his response in order to repel the confusion that occurs by making the future of the verb "beard" "al-hawwa" with waw.

2- His reliance on the sayings of the imams of the language: -

Al-Labli relied on the opinions of the imams of the language in his responses, and he responded to Abu Bakr Al-Zubaidi's opinion that the two verbs (Yagrandi, and Israndi (made, al-Labli said in his speech on what is on a weight) make me (:)) ... and this example I mean Make sure that he does not transgress at Sibawayh at all, and some of them have mentioned his transgression, and he sang: drowsiness made me repel him and make me sing. He replied the two verses (16) Abu Bakr Al-Zubaidi and said: I think they are fabricated... and not, as he said, they were mentioned by only one of the imams Linguists and grammarians such as Ibn Duraid, Abi Obaid and Karaa together, and Ibn Jinni. They were also mentioned by Abu Ali AlQali on the authority of Abi Ubaidah and Al-Lahani too. Al-Lihyani said: It is said Israndi is so-and-so and we agarda, and he sang the two verses and their meaning is one, I mean Israndi and Agrande, which is if it prevails and is superior.((17) The scholars differed in the two verbs (Islandic) meaning: Everything is ((18)), and (agrande) meaning: ((his it and his knees)) (19) in terms of necessity and transgression. So do me (he must not go beyond Sibawayh) 20), and Ibn Asfour (21), and whoever said that he transgressed Ibn Jinni (22) who believes that this weight The necessary and the transgressive come from him, and he cited the two previous verses to indicate their transgression, and al-Jawhari agreed with him in the Sahih (23). And whoever went with the necessity of weighing (do me), he went to the fact that the two verbs mentioned in the poetic verse are made, and among them is the son of Faris (24), Abu Hayyan alTawhidi (25), Ibn Asfour (26), and the owner of the crown of the bride (27), and he agreed with them from the hadith Dr. Ibrahim al-Samarrai (28), while Ibn Hisham sees him as a deviant (29), and al-Labli pointed out the validity of the two houses and the lack of I made them based on their receipt by linguists, such as Ibn Jinni (30), and Ibn Duraid in Jamhrat al-Lughah (31) and the words of al-Lihyani. It is said: And soand-so leads him, and so-and-so leads to him, and his grandsons throws him together, and so-and-so leads him and he hits him. ((32) and what It was mentioned by Abu Ubaid (33). It seems that Ibn Jinni, who said that it is permissible to transgress the two verbs, which al-Labli agreed with, looked at the two verbs Belhazin: the weight, and the meaning, it came in Sharh Al-Radhi:))... And Ibn Jinni made it sound without any abnormalities, and he divided Do I refer to a transitive and intransitive, he said: Do you use two forms of transitive and non-transitive, so the transitive is towards the saying of the transgressor) and he mentioned The house (and the non-transgressive towards their saying: the rooster warn me (()) 34). It is necessary, but if he looks at it with a note of the meaning of the act and its effect without its weight, then it is transitive. It is necessary for it (()) 35), so what effective meaning does the sentence give us: "The rooster has disappointed me"? Al-Jurjani gave an accurate description of transgression and necessity. When he said:))). Whether the verb is transitive or non-transitive is something related to the meanings and facts of the verbs, not to their words and forms. So The reality of the transgression is what has been mentioned before, that the action is an actual thing that involves something and an effective event, and the transgressor is not like that (()) 36).

3- His reliance on what was mentioned in the words of the Arabs:

After he spoke about the quadripartite verb with more two letters, which is on the weight of (verb), he indicated that it is found in the speech of the Arabs. An appendix to this weight, and a response to what Sibawayh claimed that nothing was attached to it (37), Al-Lubli said:)) He was appended to this example. I mean, do verbs, and if Sibawayh claimed that nothing had happened to him, they said: The roots of trees if their branches are many and strong. Wrapping it up, and qassar when it grows, and waning in the meaning of zall and evasion of the people

defeated, and stinging wet, and grinding if it is The rapist of the two sides says in the present tense, all of this is fa'al, qasr, za'ul, by opening the present tense and breaking the preceding. The end, as well as the measurement of everything that came on its weight (38). The more quadrilateral verb that is on the weight (do) comes to indicate an exaggeration and an increase in meaning from the original (39) and it has appendices attached to it, and al-Labli was correct in his reply. Sibawayh's opinion, when searching for the adverbs of the quadripartite verb, more on the weight of "do" I found that Ibn Jinni gave weight Appendix B (Af'al) and it is (Afa'ul) like him B (Akoula) (40), as Al-Zubaidi presented it in his correction to Sibawayh's buildings in Appendix Al-Mazeed Al-Raba'i, he said:))...and "Valo' they said: When a chick trembles, so does a man's stomach tremble while he is Kualal(() 41) and he mentioned another appendix in his book Al-Muzhar, he said: "And it is appended to Bafa'l, which is rare and white, attached to baldness (() 42).

Baqa'ar (() 42) and one of the appendices to b (do) is what came on the weight of (verbs), which is the subject of the martyrdom of al-Labli, such as: (Al-Ghan) It is said: "Al-Ghan, the plant: turned and lengthened" (43) and "Arghad" It is said: "A man is well-off, and well-groomed, he is sick."The one who was not exhausted by disease ((44), and the like of him is as long and deaf as you are, the one who has been reduced to And (do) such as: (asmar) (48), and these verbs that follow the weight (do) indicate the correctness of his response, and indicate the extent of its accuracy. in tracking verb suffixes.

4- His dependence on homogenization.

It came in his transfer of Illal (says, and sells) by transferring the movement of their eyes to what is before them:)) ... they inhabited it in the present tense and threw She moved it according to what was before it.

I mean, they transferred the damma al-'ayn to the fa' in the present tense, so they said in he says: he says, and in sells: he sells. So the eye was inhabited and before it a hug, and if the waw joined what preceded it, it would have been possible for it. This is what we mentioned from the present disorder Because of the heavy movement in the ya and waw, it was moved to what came before it, so it was used by many grammarians, and it is weak because The waw and the yaa, if the preceding them resides in the course of the correct, and the movement in them does not become heavy (49) This is his opinion in rejecting that The reason for the transference is to avoid the heaviness that occurs by keeping the movement on the same verb. He gave this opinion which. He described it as weak in another response, in which he said: "But what should be said: These actions that are defective in the eye are only obligatory. In which the accusatives are in the present tense for the sake of the past ills Following on from the past, lest one of them be healthy and the other defective, they turned it back in the past, because what came before it is open, and they did not find She moved it according to what came before it, but they inhabited it, so they turned it so that their hearts would be a thousand, indicating that it was mobile, because if They left it still because it resembled saying and selling and they are two sources, so they made before it a thousand evidence of what we mentioned (() 50. The accusatives between the past and present verbs necessitate the follower, and Ibn Jinni al-Labli previously came to this opinion. The fair one:)) ... So when the present came, they raised it up in order to follow the past so that one of them would not be correct and the other would be defective, so they transferred. The damma and the kasrah from the waw and the ya to what came before them, and make them dwell in them, so it became (says, sells, and lengthens) (...as for gold. Until ((he says, sells)) and towards them, but the movement in them was heavy in the waw and the yaa, so it was transferred to what was before them, so they became silent. So he is not filled with his saying, because if the waw and the yaa are inhabited by what precedes them, they follow the course of the saheeh, and the movement in them is not weighted (51) Ibn Asfour also went to this opinion (52), and it must be pointed out that al-Labli's refusal was the fact that weighting was a cause of Illustration by transmission, and his response to this issue is that ((If what preceded them was inhabited, following the course of the Sahih, the movement was not burdensome. In both of them (((There is a consideration, because the waw and ya run the course of the correct letter if the preceding them dwells, it is stipulated that they be in The location of the letters of the Arabic language is Karma, Ghazu, Debi, here the case is different in (says, and sells), because the waw and the yaa did not occur.

The position of the arabic letter that comes at the end of the word, and this was confirmed by al-Mazini (53). Scholars (54) however, differed interpretations of the reasons for transmission, in addition to the advanced interpretations, some of them are gold Until the weakness of the vowels and the hardship that they endure for the vowels is what led to the transfer of the vowel vowel movement to the one before it (55). It seems from the foregoing that al-Labli, in his previous reply, was not particularly interested in the linguistic use of pronunciation as much as he was logical reasoning of the rules.

5- His reliance on morphological rules and arguing with them in his responses.

It was mentioned in the chapter of Al-Mahmouz): If it is based on a verb with the conquest, then its present comes in two ways, as for the adverb as you say He took taking... and as for the break as you say, "Remove it, remove it..." and deviate from this section by only one letter. They said: "I refuse to refuse." It came upon a verb to do, opening the eyes of both the past and the future, and we have mentioned it. Some of them said: But it was opened to pay it Hamza, which is one of the letters of the throat, and this is wrong. Because the letters of the throat only affect if they are moving in the eye or lama and the hamza Here in yabi is sakina and it is faa, it is not effective as presented (56) Al-Labli adopted the morphological rule in his reply that he mentioned The

morphologists in their books (57) justify opening the eye of the present tense verb, which has the right to be the subject of the eye (to do) or Broken eye (verb) from the past on the weight of (verb) in that the present tense verb eye opens if it is the eye or Laam is one of the letters of the throat, and it is clear from his saying:)) This is wrong. Because the letters of the throat only affect if they are A moving eye or a llama, and the hamza here in Yabi is static, and it is a faa, so it is not effective (() 58). He relied on the response to The three parameters are: the letter of the throat, the position, and the sukoon. At the outset, it must be noted that linguists The ancients counted the hamza as one of the laryngeal letters (59), including al-Labli, while the modernists counted it as one of the laryngeal letters (60). It is a strong voice, neither in the neglected nor in the whispered (61). And the letters of the throat are the heaviest letters, so the eyes were opened to resist This weight (62), the fathah, as it is known, is the lightest of movements, so al-Labli argued that the hamza in (Yabi) came silent. In order for it to perform its function, it is supposed to be mobile. The issue of location was also an argument for refuting Al-Lubli. The present tense verb (yabi) did not come with an eye or a llama, but rather a fa'i in the position, and the fa' does not affect the same as the 'ayn and the lam. The eye is the balance of the word, and the lam is the site of the word's inflection, and it would have been better for al-Labli to respond to what he narrated from them His saying:)) Some of them said: It is only opened because its fa'ah is a hamza, which is a letter from the halal letters ((63) that the verb is present in the present tense. He commands (Fa'ah is a hamza, which is one of the letters of the throat, although it did not open the essence of the verb, but rather came joined according to the rule. Sibawayh had an opinion on the issue of Ayn (Abi), so once he made it similar to the present tense verb read, he said: ((And they said: My father refused, so they likened him to reading (() 64) The Serafi said in explaining this text:

“He meant that they resembled the hamzah that is in the beginning of my father. And it is the fulfillment of the verb from it with the hamza which is a lama in the example of a recital reciting, so they opened the eye of the verb for the sake of the fa', as they opened it For the sake of al-lam, which is a hamza (() 65), and again he used it on the basis of the original, and likened it to (it is reckoned), he said:) and in Another aspect refuses, which is that it be like it is calculated, it was opened as it was broken (() 66), and some of them see that the eye was opened Because the alif is because the alif is from the exposition of al-Hamza (67), and al-Sirafi replied by saying: It is not an origin in Abi Yabi, but rather it is reversed from Ya I refuse to open up what preceded it (68). From the foregoing, we can say that al-Labli was weaving his response by collecting the various directions of the issue as is clear from his consideration for (my father) with the notes of the nature of the letter, the position, and the sukoon

6- Relying on context in response:

Speaking about verbs that do not act, he said: “These six verbs do not use the present or the adjective. Not at all, even if Abd al-Da'im al-Qayrawani had said in his book, Hila al-'Ala, that he may have used an adjective from him. He said: He said

Abu Al-Ala Al-Maari:

Would you excuse me if I fell short in my praises, for my example is in forsaking the qurayd?

And what he said is wrong, because “Ess” is in the house, meaning “created and true.” Al-Labli relied in his response on the meaning of what he had inspired from the context of the poetic verse, as Al-Ma'arri (d. 449 AH) describes himself. By al-'Asi, i.e., created and true, by abandoning al-Qurayd, the rules of poetry systems. Creativity is exercise. From that, you say to the one who has learned something, it has become a character for him, i.e., he has become accustomed to it and has become accustomed to it ((70)). It is as if abandoning poetry has become familiar to Al-

Ma'arri for several reasons. From her he grew old, he died at the age of

The eighty-four years old, on the one hand, and on the other hand blinded him, so he was nicknamed Burheen al-Mahbasin: meaning Mahbas. Blindness, and imprisoning the house, because he retired from people after his return from Baghdad until his death. It must be pointed out that perhaps its lexical meaning denotes arrogance. It came in Tahdheeb AlLughah: He grew up and grew up: he is arrogant and arrogant, and he is as arrogant as he is and Al-Layth said: “May the sheikh be stubborn and wretched when he grows up (71). As for “may” the meaning of greed and pity, it is far from the meaning of the poetic verse.

References

- Al-Abdal, Abu Al-Tayyib Abdul-Wahed Bin Ali Al-Lughi (d. 351 A.H.), investigated by: Izz Al-Din Al-Tanoukhi, d. Publications of the Arab Scientific Academy, Damascus, Syria, 1379 A.H. 1960 A.D.
 Recognizing beatings from Lisan al-Arab, Abu Hayyan al-Andalusi (d. 745 AH), investigation, explanation and study: Rajab
 Othman Muhammad, referenced: Ramadan Abdel-Tawab, 1st edition, Al-Khanji Library, Cairo, 1418 AH - 1998 AD.
 Remediation on Sibawayh in the book “The Buildings and Ziyadat” according to what was mentioned in it politely, Abu Bakr Muhammad bin Al-Hassan

- Al-Ashbili Al-Zubaidi (d. 379 A.H.), taken care of: the orientalist Ignatius Quaidy, printed in Rome 1890 A.D.
- 4- Linguistic sounds, Dr. Ibrahim Anis, Ibrahim Anis, d., Anglo-Egyptian Library, Egypt, 1999 AD.
- The Origins of Grammar, Abu Bakr Muhammad bin Sahel bin Al-Sarraj AlNahawi Al-Baghdadi (d. 316 A.H), investigated by: Abd Al-Hussein Al-Fatli, d.t., d.t.
- Al-Afaal, Abu Othman Saeed bin Muhammad Al-Ma'afari Al-Saraqusti, investigative by: Dr. Hussain Muhammad Muhammad Sharaf,
- Review: Muhammad Mahdi Allam, d., General Authority for Amiri Press Affairs, Cairo, 1395 AH 1975 AD.
- Al-Afaal, Abu al-Qasim Ali bin Jaafar al-Saadi, known as Ibn al-Qatta' (died 515 AH), i 1, Dar al-Maaref Ottoman, Hyderabad Deccan, 1360 AD.
- 8- Clarification of what is hidden in the tail on revealing suspicions about the names of books and arts, Ismail Pasha bin Muhammad Amin Al-Baghdadi (died 1339 AH), corrected by: Muhammad Sharaf al-Din Baltaqaya, and Rifaat Belka al-Kilisi, d., Dar. Reviving the Arab Heritage, Beirut, Lebanon, d.
- With the aim of hopes to know the futures of verbs, Abu Jaafar al-Labli (d. 691 AH), investigated by: Jaafar Majid, d. Tunisian publishing house, 1972 AD.
- Pursuing the Consciousness in the Layers of Linguists and Grammarians, Jalal alDin Abd al-Rahman al-Suyuti (died 911 AH), investigated by: Muhammad Abu AlFadl Ibrahim, d., Issa Al-Babi Al-Halabi and Co. Press, 1384 A.H. 1964 A.D.
- The bride's crown from the jewels of the dictionary, by Imam Muhib Al-Din Abi Fayd Al-Sayyid Muhammad Murtada Al-Husseini Al-Wasiti Al-Zubaidi Al-Hanafi (d. 1205 A.H), Investigated by Ali Sherry, Dr. Dar Al-Fikr for Printing, Publishing and Distribution, Beirut Lebanon, 1414 A.H. 1994 A.D.
- The language crowd, the author: Abu Bakr Muhammad ibn al-Hasan ibn Duraid al-Azdi (died 321 AH) Investigator: Ramzi Munir Baalbaki Publisher: Dar Al-Ilm for Millions, Beirut, Edition: First, - 1987 AD.
- Characteristics, Abu Fath Othman bin Jinni (died 392 AH), investigation: Muhammad Ali Al-Najjar, 4th edition, The Egyptian Authority General Book, 1999 AD.
- The State of Islam in Andalusia, Muhammad Abdullah Anan, 4th edition, AlKhanji Library, Cairo, 1417 AH - 1997 AD.
- 15 The Journey of Al-Abdari, Abu Abdullah Al-Abdari, investigation: Ali Ibrahim Kurdi, 2nd edition, Dar Saad Al-Din for printing publishing and distribution.
- Explanation of Shafia Ibn al-Hajib, Radhi al-Din Muhammad ibn al-Hasan al-Istrabadi (d. 686 AH), investigation: Muhammad Nour Al-Hassan, Muhammad AlZafzaf, Muhammad Muhyi Al-Din Abd Al-Hamid, Dar Al-Kutub Al-Ilmiyya, Beirut, Lebanon, 1402 AH. 1982 AD.
- Explanation of Sibawayh's book, Abu Saeed Al Serafi Al Hassan bin Abdullah bin Al Marzban (died 368 AH), investigation: Ahmed Hassan Mahdali, and Ali Sayed Ali, Dar al-Kutub al-Ilmiyya, Beirut, Lebanon, 1429 AH 2008 AD.
- Al-Sahah, Al-Jawhari (d. 393 AH), investigated by Ahmed Abdel Ghafour AlAttar, 4th edition, Dar Al-Ilm for Millions, Beirut, Lebanon, 1407.
- Phonology, Bertil Malmberg, Arabization and Study: Dr. Abdel-Sabour Shaheen, d., Youth Library, Cairo, 1984 AD.
- General Linguistics (Voices), Dr. Kamal Bishr, 4th floor, Dar Al Maaref, Egypt, 1970 AD.
- Mayor of the Exchange, Dr. Kamal Ibrahim, d.T., Al-Zahraa Press, Baghdad, 1376 A.H.
- 22 Al-Amd fi Kitab Al-Tasrif, Abdul Qafer bin Abdul Rahman Al-Jarjani, Investigated by Al-Badrawi Zahran, 3rd Edition. Dar Al-Maaref, Cairo, 1995.
23. The title of Al-Daraya among the scholars in the seventh century in Bejaia, Abu Al-Abbas Al-Ghubrini Ahmed bin Ahmed bin Abdullah (644 A.H. 714 A.H.), investigation and commentary: Adel Noueihed, 2nd Edition, Consultations of the New Horizons House, Beirut, Lebanon, 1979.
- 24 The Action, Its Time and Its Buildings, Dr. Ibrahim Al-Samarrai, Dr. Al-Madani Press, Baghdad, 1386 A.H. - 1966 A.D.
25. Al-Kafi in Morphology, Dr. Firas Abdul-Aziz Abdul-Qader Al-Kadawi, Dr. Abdul-Wahhab Muhammad Ali Al-Adwani, Dr. I, Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, University of Mosul, 1439 AH 2008 AD.
- 26 Sibawayh's book, Abu Bishr Amr bin Othman bin Qanbar, investigation: Abd alSalam Muhammad Harun, 1st edition, Dar al-Jeel Beirut, Lebanon, Dr. T.
- Uncovering suspicions about the names of books and arts, Haji Khalifa (d. 1067), correction and commentary: Muhammad Sharaf Al-Din Yaltaqaya, and Rifaat Belka Al-Kilisi, d., House of Revival of Arab Heritage, Beirut, Lebanon, d.T.
- Treasure of Preservation in the book Tahdhib al-Lafwaa, by al-Khatib al-Tabrizi, compiled and controlled by: Father Louis Sheikho the Jesuit. The Catholic Press of the Jesuit Fathers, Beirut, Lebanon, 1895 AD.

- Lisan al-Arab, Ibn Manzur (711 AH), corrected by Muhammad Amin Abd alWahhab, Muhammad al-Sadiq al-Obaidi, 3rd edition, Arab Heritage Revival House, Arab History Foundation, Beirut, Lebanon, 1419 AH 1999 AD.
- Al-Mubdaa fi Al-Tasrif, Abu Hayyan Al-Nahwi Al-Andalusi (d. 745 AH), investigated by Abdul Hamid Al-Sayyid Talib, 1st Edition, Dar Al-Urubah for Publishing and Distribution, Kuwait, 1402 A.H., 1982 A.D
- Al-Shafia Group in the science of morphology and calligraphy (Explanation of Al-Jarbardī (d. 746 AH), and Sharh Naqra (d. 776 AH).
- And a footnote on the explanation of Al-Jarbardī by Ibn Jama`ah (d. 879 AH), and the sufficient methods in explaining the Shafia by Zakaria
- Al-Ansari (died 936 AH), and the great benefits in the explanation of the beautiful Fara'id Ibrahim (d. 1016 AH), Muhammad Abd Salam Shaheen, Scientific Books House, Beirut, Lebanon.
- Introduction to the Science of Arabic Phonetics, Dr. Ghanem Qaddouri AlHamad, Edition 1, Dar Ammar, Jordan, 1425 A.H. 2004 AD.
- 33 Introduction to Linguistics and Linguistic Research Methods, Dr. Ramadan AbdelTawab, 3rd Edition, Al-Khanji Library For printing, publishing and distribution, Cairo, 1417 AH 1997 AD.
34. Al-Mizhar in the Sciences of Language and its Kinds, Abd al-Hamman Jalal alDin al-Suyuti (died 911 AH), investigated by: Muhammad Ahmad Gad Al-Mawla, Muhammad Abu Al-Fadl Ibrahim, Ali Muhammad Al-Bajawi, 3rd floor, Dar AlTurath Library, Cairo, d.T.
- 35- Mujam Al-Buldan, Shihab Al-Din Abi Abdullah Yaqt bin Abdullah Al-Hamawi Al-Rumi Al-Baghdadi (d. 626 AH), d. Arab Heritage Revival House, Beirut, Lebanon, 1399 A.H. - 1979 A.D.
36. Dictionary of Phonology, Muhammad Ali Al-Khouli, d., Dar Al-Falah for Publishing and Distribution, Jordan, 1998 AD.
- 37 Authors' Dictionary, Omar Reda Kahala, d., House of Revival of Arab Heritage, Beirut, Lebanon, and Al-Muthanna Library, Beirut, d.T.
38. Mughni Al-Labib on the books of the Arabs, Muhammad Abdullah Jamal Al-Din bin Hisham Al-Ansari (d. 761 AH), investigation : Muhammad Mohieddin Abd alHamid, 1st Edition, Al-Sadiq Foundation for Printing and Publishing, Iran, 1386 AH.
- 39- Language Standards, by Abu Al-Hussein Ahmed Bin Faris Bin Zakaria (395 A.H.), achieved by Abd Al-Salam Muhammad Haroun, Dar Al-Fikr for printing, publishing and distribution, d. i, d. NS .
- Al-Muqtada fi Sharh Al-Edah, Abdul Qaher Al-Jarjani, investigation: Kazem Bahr Al-Murjan, d., Publications. The Ministry of Culture and Information, Republic of Iraq, Heritage Books Series (115), Dar Al-Rasheed Publishing, 1982.
- Al-Mumti' al-Kabeer fi al-Tasrif, Ibn Asfour al-Ashbili (d. 669 AH), investigated by: Fakhr al-Din Qabawah, 1st Edition, Lebanon Library, Publishers, 1996.
- Al-Munsef fi Kitab Al-Tasrif, Abu Al-Fath Othman bin Jinni (392 A.H.), investigated by: Ibrahim Mustafa, Abdullah Amin, 1st floor, Ministry of Public Education, Department of Reviving Ancient Heritage, Mustafa Al-Babi Al-Halabi Library And his sons, 1373 AH 1954 AD.
- Nuzha Al-Mushtaq in Breaking Through the Horizons, by Abu Abdullah Muhammad bin Abdullah bin Idris Al-Hamwi Al-Hasani, the well-known Al-Sharif Al-Idrisi (one of the scholars of the sixth century AH), Dr. Al-Taqqafa Religious Library, Cairo, 1422 AH 2002 AD.
- A good smell from the fresh branch of Andalusia, Ahmed bin Muhammad AlMaqri Al-Tilmisani, investigation: Dr. Ihsan Abbas, Dr. T., Dar Sader, Beirut, 1388 AH 1968 AD.
- Hadiya Al-Arefin, Ismail Pasha Al-Baghdadi (d. 1339 AH) d., House of Revival of Arab Heritage, Beirut, Lebanon. d.t.
- Al-Wafi in Deaths, Al-Safadi (d. 764 AH), investigated by: Ahmad Al-Arnaout, and Turki Mustafa, d., Ihya House Heritage, Beirut, Lebanon 1420 AH 2000 AD.

Author Information

Ghaidaa Kadhim Abdullah

College of Agriculture, University of Al-Qadisiyah,
Iraq
